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PATHOMORPHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF DIFFUSE ADENOMYOSIS

Introduction. According to data from the World Health Organization, endometriosis affects approximately 10% (190 million) of women and girls of reproductive age worldwide, and its prevalence continues to rise. As a result, this condition is classified as a modern epidemic (WHO, 2022)

Keywords: Endometriosis, adenomyosis, “junction zone”, extracellular matrix

Materials and methods: In the research of the pathomorphological features of uterine adenomyosis, uterine tissues from women with various causes of bleeding, endometrial adenomatous hyperplasia, and other reasons were collected from amputated uterine specimens.

Research results: In the majority of cases, the endometrial glandular epithelium showed a variety of structures, stained with basophilic and eosinophilic dyes. In the subendometrial regions of the myometrium, bundles of muscle fibers are distributed, with small-caliber arterial blood vessels and oval-shaped venous vessels interspersed in the interstitial space. No clear morphological features characteristic of the “junctional zone” were identified between the endometrium and myometrium.

Morphological classification based on the information obtained from the stained micronutrients using the Trichrome (Van Gieson + Masson + Weigert) method showed the following.cc

In the basal layer of the endometrium, intense staining of various types of fibrous structures in the extracellular matrix was observed. Collagen fibers of various thicknesses were present around the blood vessels and glands, and the same collagen fibers were located around the myocyte bundles at the interface between the myometrium and endometrium. The similarities in the structural features of the collagen fibers indicate that similar changes are likely to occur in pathologies. To identify the boundaries between the myometrium and endometrium, the “Hamamatsu NanoZoomer” histoscan device was used to scan tissue preparations measuring 1.5x2.0 cm. The obtained micronutrient samples were measured using NDP.view 2+ and ImageJ software. The length of the area measured between the endometrium and myometrium was 6.35mm (6350 μm).The main morphological substrate between the proportional boundaries of the endometrium and myometrium is characterized by the presence of gray and green collagen fibers, which are stained similarly in the extracellular matrix (Masson’s trichrome stain is specifically used to stain fibrous structures in the walls of arteries and capillaries). The endometrium, by its nature, primarily consists of epithelial cells, glandular epithelium, and mesenchymal components such as histiocytes, fibroblasts, fibrous structures, blood vessels, and capillaries, with the glandular epithelium forming the core of its parenchyma. The myometrial layer, on the other hand, is primarily composed of mesenchymal tissues, smooth muscle bundles, blood vessels, capillaries, and interspersed fibrous structures. The boundaries between these layers, according to clinical instrumental examinations, are typically found to be approximately 5 mm (5000 microns), and for precision in our study, we selected boundary measurements of 6350 microns to avoid any ambiguity. Through our main research findings, the proportional

relationships between the boundaries of the uterine endometrium and myometrium were determined by measuring the area occupied by muscle, blood vessels, and fibrous structures using confocal multiplex morphometry. This provided data that clarified our study, particularly in identifying the “junctional zone” and its contributions to the endometrial area. We focused on the structures with the highest proportion of similar components, primarily collagen fibers of type 1. Based on the obtained results, the transitional zone, with the myometrial layer forming its primary area, showed a ratio of 3.25:1.75 (65% of the area occupied by the myometrium, 35% by the endometrial basal layer). This was the specific proportion determined.

Conclusion: The primary substrate of the morphological changes is explained by the sharp expansion of the basal layer boundary between the endometrium and myometrium, the expansion of the basal layer interposition, and the formation of coarse collagen fiber structures in various concentric patterns, along with the hyperchromatic, large nucleated appearance of myocyte clusters. The glandular structures in the myometrial layer were found to have an oval and elongated appearance, with epithelial metaplasia and vacuolar dystrophy.

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